

THIS STUDY PORTFOLIO FOR THE AFTERHERNIA PROJECT REPRESENTS THE PLANNED INDIVIDUAL STUDIES AS OF MAY 28, 2024,

TABLE I: GROIN HERNIA STUDY PORTFOLIO

Study #	Study aims
1	Validation of the AHQ-groin questionnaire.
2	The impact of mesh weight on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
3	The impact of mesh weight on the risk of long-term surgical complications in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
4	The impact of mesh weight on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in open surgery of groin hernias.
5	Absorbable tacks vs. permanent tacks as mesh fixation and their impact on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
6	Closure of peritoneum with self-locking suture in TAPP repair and its impact on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
7	Closure of peritoneum with self-locking suture in TAPP repair and the risk of long-term surgical complications in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
8	Young vs. older and the impact on patient-reported outcomes for patients undergoing open surgery of groin hernias.
9	Young vs. older and the risk of long-term surgical complications for patients undergoing laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
10	Mesh fixation and its impact on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
11	Mesh fixation and the risk of long-term surgical complications in laparoscopic surgery of groin hernias.
12	Self-reported recurrence vs. reoperation: Investigating whether previous findings regarding the ratio between recurrence and reoperation for patients with groin hernias are still relevant.
13	Surgeons' operation volume and its impact on patient-reported outcomes for patients operated for groin hernias.

- 14 Surgeons' operation volume and the risk of long-term surgical complications for patients operated for groin hernias.
- 15 Investigation on whether smoking and obesity are risk factors for poor patient reported outcomes
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TABLE 2: VENTRAL HERNIA STUDY PORTFOLIO

Study #	Study aims
1	The impact of mesh weight on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in ventral hernia surgery performed using the onlay method.
2	The impact of mesh weight the risk of long-term surgical complications in ventral hernia surgery performed using the onlay method.
3	Mesh vs. non-mesh and the impact on patient-reported outcomes in open ventral hernia surgery.
4	Mesh vs. non-mesh and the risk of long-term surgical complications in open ventral hernia surgery.
5	The impact of mesh weight on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in ventral hernia surgery performed using the IPOM (Intraperitoneal Onlay Mesh) method.
6	The impact of mesh weight on risk of long-term surgical complications in ventral hernia surgery performed using the IPOM method.
7	Absorbable tacks vs. permanent tacks as mesh fixation and their impact on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in ventral hernia surgery using the IPOM method.
8	Absorbable tacks vs. permanent tacks as mesh fixation and their impact on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence in ventral hernia surgery performed using the IPOM method.
9	Onlay vs. preperitoneal vs. intraperitoneal placement of mesh and its impact on patient-reported outcomes and recurrence for patients with ventral hernias.
10	Onlay vs. preperitoneal vs. intraperitoneal placement of mesh and the risk of long-term surgical complications for patients with ventral hernias.
11	Young vs. older and the impact on patient-reported outcomes for patients operated for ventral hernias.
12	Young vs. older and the risk of long-term surgical complications for patients operated for ventral hernias.

- 13 Self-reported recurrence vs. reoperation: Investigating whether previous findings regarding the ratio between recurrence and reoperation for patients with ventral hernias are still relevant.
- 14 Surgeons' operation volume and its impact on patient-reported outcomes for patients operated for ventral hernias.
- 15 Surgeons' operation volume and the risk of long-term surgical complications for patients operated for ventral hernias.
- 16 PFAS vs other mesh and its effect on patient reported outcomes and recurrence in ventral hernia repair
- 17 Investigation on whether smoking and obesity are risk factors for poor patient reported outcomes
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